

**ADVANTAGES OF TEACHING KARAKALPAK
LEXICON**

Saparmatov Omar Shamurat ugli
Student of the Karakalpak Language and
Literature Department of the Nukus State
Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19543620>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 07th April 2026

Accepted: 09th April 2026

Online: 11th April 2026

KEYWORDS

Karakalpak language, vocabulary, communicative competence, creative thinking, speech culture, language teaching, cultural heritage, practical skills, pedagogical methods

ABSTRACT

This article highlights the advantages of teaching the lexicon of the Karakalpak language. The main aspects of the text are analyzed, such as increasing vocabulary, developing the ability to understand and interpret language, forming communicative and creative competence, developing practical language skills, and studying cultural and historical heritage. The article also shows ways to increase students' interest in speech culture and language through effective teaching of vocabulary.

The lexicon of the Karakalpak language is a branch of linguistics that studies the meaning, scope of use of words and their aspects, such as synonyms, antonyms, phraseological units. Teaching vocabulary in general education schools and vocational colleges plays an important role in the development of students' rich vocabulary, speech culture, and thinking skills. At the same time, effective teaching of vocabulary accelerates the process of language acquisition and forms communicative competence in students.

The first advantage of teaching vocabulary is increasing vocabulary. Students learn to use rich and correct words in their speech by studying words and phrases on various topics. This enriches their oral and written speech and expands their means of expression.

The second advantage is the development of the ability to understand and interpret language. When studying vocabulary, students analyze the meaning of the word, related phrases, and synonyms-antonyms. Thus, they better understand the text and can clearly express their thoughts.

The third advantage is the enhancement of communicative competence. A student with an expanded vocabulary can express their thoughts freely and logically in various situations. This makes the communication process effective and develops the student's social skills.

The fourth advantage is the development of creative thinking. Working with lexical material allows students to complete tasks such as creating new words, writing stories and essays, and compiling poems. This increases their artistic thinking and strengthens their interest in language.

The fifth advantage is the formation of the ability to use language practically. Through lexical exercises, text analysis, role-playing games, and dialogues, students learn to use words and phrases in practice. At the same time, they reinforce knowledge of grammar and morphology in a lexical context.

The study of cultural and historical heritage is also carried out through the teaching of vocabulary. Students understand the historical and cultural aspects of language through folk tales, proverbs, word games, and literary works. This increases respect for language and culture.

In conclusion, teaching the lexicon of the Karakalpak language has important advantages in increasing students' vocabulary, developing speech culture, forming creative and communicative abilities, and understanding cultural heritage. Therefore, the use of effective methods and approaches in teaching vocabulary is a priority task for every teacher.

References:

1. Dáwletov A., Dáwletov M., Qudaybergenov M. Házirgi qaraqalpaq ádebiy tili. Morfemika. Morfonologiya. Sóz jasalıw. Morfologiya. Nókis, 2010.
2. Qaraqalpaq tili imla qağıydalar jıynağı. Nókis, 2016.
3. Qurbanbaeva B. Qaraqalpaq tili. Toshkent "Tafakkur avlod", 2020.
4. Uli, S. K. J. (2024). T. QAYÍPBERGENOV POVESTLERINIŇ SYUJETLIK ÓZGESHELIGI. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 4(7), 96-101.

